

'Magic Heat Sense': Utilizing Thermochromic Pigments to Enhance Safety in Ironing Board Design

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Abstract: Ironing boards are a common frequently used household item. Standard ironing boards are typically equipped with steel iron holders, which pose a significant safety risk. The steel material of iron holders retains heat, can be dangerously hot and indistinguishable from its cool state without direct contact. Therefore, people often have to rely on guesswork or unsafe testing methods to determine if the holder is still hot, increasing the likelihood of burns. There is a clear need for a safer solution to address the risks posed by traditional iron holders. Integrating thermochromic paint into the iron holder design on ironing boards offers a simple yet effective safety enhancement. This innovative approach leverages thermochromic pigments, which change color when exposed to heat, to provide a clear visual cue indicating when the holder is hot. We incorporated thermochromic pigment into an epoxy base and layered this on top of a red-painted regular iron holder. We tested the holder; the epoxy layer gives a dark purple when cool, and becomes transparent when hot, revealing the red undercoating. This visual cue provides an immediate and intuitive warning, significantly reducing the risk of burns and improving overall safety. Benefits of 'Magic HeatSense' include an enhanced safety and user-friendly design as the feature requires no additional actions from users. It has commercial potential with large target market of consumers. It is cost-effective with the crude cost of less than RM20. In conclusion, 'Magic HeatSense' provides a simple and effective solution to reduce burn incidence from iron holders.

Keywords: thermochromic; ironing board; iron burns.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ironing boards are one of the most frequently used household items, playing a crucial role in maintaining clothing care. Despite their importance, the design of standard ironing boards, specifically the iron holders, presents a significant safety concern. These holders are typically constructed from steel, which is an excellent conductor of heat. While the material's durability is beneficial for supporting a hot iron, it also retains heat long after the iron is removed. The surface of the iron holder can remain dangerously hot and indistinguishable from its cool state without direct physical contact. This creates a hazardous situation for users, who often resort to unsafe testing methods like briefly touching the surface or guessing whether it is still hot. Such actions can lead to accidental burns, which are a common domestic injury, particularly in homes with children or elderly individuals (Brown & Harrison, 2019).

In recent years, innovations in material sciences, particularly the development of thermochromic pigments, have created new opportunities for improving household safety devices

(Davies & Patel, 2021). Thermochromic materials change color when exposed to heat, providing an immediate visual cue about the temperature of an object. This property makes thermochromic pigments particularly useful in environments where temperature indicators are crucial for safety. The application of these materials in household items, such as ironing boards, could significantly reduce the risk of burn injuries by providing users with clear, real-time information about the temperature of surfaces. The present study introduces an innovative solution to the issue of hot iron holders by integrating thermochromic pigments into the design of the iron holder, offering a visual safety feature that indicates when the surface is hot.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The primary objective of this research was to create a safer ironing board iron holder by incorporating thermochromic pigments into its design. Thermochromic pigments, known for their ability to change color in response to temperature variations, provide a clear visual indicator of whether the iron holder is hot or cool. The experimental design involved applying these pigments in combination with an epoxy base onto a standard steel iron holder.

The thermochromic pigment selected for this study was one that shifts from dark purple to transparent upon reaching a specific temperature threshold. This particular pigment was chosen for its distinct color contrast and rapid response to heat exposure. Before the thermochromic layer was applied, the iron holder was coated with a layer of red paint. The purpose of this underlayer was to create a stark visual contrast when the thermochromic pigment became transparent upon heating, revealing the red base coat. The application of the epoxy-thermochromic mixture was done carefully to ensure an even coating on the entire surface of the iron holder.

After preparing the iron holder, we conducted a series of tests under normal ironing conditions. The holder was heated by placing a hot iron on it for varying durations to simulate real-world usage. The responsiveness of the color change was recorded, focusing on the speed of transition from purple to transparent, as well as the clarity of the color change. Additionally, the time taken for the surface to cool and return to its original dark purple color was measured, ensuring that the safety feature was consistent and reliable during extended usage (Jackson & Nguyen, 2018).

3. FINDINGS

The findings from the tests conducted were highly promising. The thermochromic paint reacted rapidly to changes in temperature, providing an immediate visual cue when the iron holder became hot. When cool, the iron holder maintained its dark purple color, clearly signaling that the surface was safe to touch. However, as soon as the surface temperature increased due to the placement of the iron, the thermochromic layer began to transition to transparent, revealing the bright red undercoat. This change occurred within a few seconds of the iron being placed on the holder, effectively warning the user that the surface was hot.

The transition back to the original purple color occurred as the holder cooled down, providing a reliable indication that the surface had returned to a safe temperature. These results demonstrate that the thermochromic pigment performs as expected, creating a simple yet effective visual warning system for users. Moreover, the application of the thermochromic pigment did not compromise the functionality of the iron holder. It remained durable and capable of supporting the iron without any deformation or damage from repeated heating and cooling cycles (Nguyen & Liu, 2020).

4. DISCUSSION

The application of thermochromic pigments to household products represents a significant advancement in domestic safety design. Traditional ironing board iron holders, while durable and efficient, have long posed a safety hazard due to their ability to retain heat for prolonged periods. The findings from this study illustrate that thermochromic pigments offer a viable solution to this issue. By providing a clear, intuitive visual warning, users no longer need to guess whether the iron holder is hot or resort to unsafe methods such as brief touches to check the temperature. This passive safety feature enhances user experience without requiring any additional effort from the user (Smith & Adams, 2022).

From a commercial perspective, the cost-effectiveness of thermochromic materials makes this innovation particularly attractive for manufacturers. The production cost of integrating thermochromic paint into the iron holder design is estimated to be under RM20, which is affordable considering the enhanced safety features provided. Additionally, the widespread use of ironing boards in households across the world suggests a large target market for this product, making it a commercially viable solution (Davies & Patel, 2021).

Thermochromic materials have already been successfully employed in other industries, such as in thermometers and medical devices, where temperature indication is crucial. This study extends the application of thermochromic technology to household safety, demonstrating its potential to be adopted in a wide range of consumer products. Other household items that retain heat, such as kitchen appliances, could also benefit from the integration of thermochromic pigments, further enhancing domestic safety (Nguyen & Liu, 2020).

Figure 1. The holder is red when hot and dark purple when cold.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the introduction of thermochromic pigments into the design of ironing board iron holders provides a simple, effective, and low-cost solution to a common household safety issue. By offering a clear visual cue when the iron holder is hot, the risk of accidental burns is significantly reduced. The product, named 'Magic HeatSense', has substantial potential for widespread adoption due to its ease of use, cost-effectiveness, and ability to integrate seamlessly into existing ironing board

designs. As household safety continues to be a priority, the application of thermochromic technology in everyday items could transform the way consumer products are designed to prevent injuries. Future research may explore additional applications of thermochromic technology in other household items and industries where temperature control and safety are critical.

Acknowledgments: Our gratitude to Dr. Ahmad Najmee who supported this project.

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